

Intelligent Machines for Autonomous Robotics and Manipulation: Combining Soft Robotics, Deep Learning and Human Inspiration

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I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

THE execution of reliable and stable grasping with artificial hands is a main challenge in the robotics field, due to its practical relevance and theoretical complexity. The *classic* approach used to grasp with rigid robotic hands generally favored object-centric analytical solutions. More specifically, a set of available contact points is hypothesized, while their position and contact forces are evaluated from the object knowledge [1]. Although very elegant and theoretically sound, this approach has not yet produced the desired outcomes in practice. To address these limitations, in soft artificial hands part of the control intelligence has been directly embedded in their mechanism, through the purposeful introduction of elastic elements and under-actuation patterns [2], [3]. Thanks to their intrinsic compliance, soft hands can mold around the external items and exploit their environment, thus multiplying their grasping capabilities, similarly to humans.

Several papers have shown that soft end-effectors can achieve high-level grasping performance when operated by humans (see e.g. [4], [5]). However, such level of dexterity is still unmatched in autonomous grasp execution. This represents an important challenge not only for industrial applications but also for advanced human-robot interaction. Indeed, as of today, robots are no more in their *cages* – where they originally acted in industrial pipelines for accomplishing precise yet repetitive tasks – but actively interact with humans as assistive devices or co-bots, facing action execution in unstructured environments. Under this regard, the compliance of the mechanical structure of soft systems and hands not only enables a safe interaction with humans, but it also allows a purposeful adaptation with respect to different object shapes, for manipulation purposes. However, *classic* approaches cannot be applied to this kind of hands, which - by their own nature - do not allow fingertips placement with the required precision and relative independence. On the contrary, data driven approaches could be the key to learn from humans how to manage soft hands, towards higher levels of autonomous grasping capabilities.

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Figure 1: High level organization of the proposed architecture, which combines anticipatory actions and reactive behavior. A deep classifier looks at the scene and predicts the strategy that a human operator would use to grasp the object. This output is employed to select the corresponding robotic primitive. These primitives define the posture of the hand over time, to produce a natural, human-like motion. The IMUs placed on the fingers of the hand detect the contact with the items and triggers a suitable reactive grasp behavior.

Recently machine learning – and in particular deep learning – has become very popular for grasping generation, with positive results [6], [7]. However, so far only few works in literature have applied learning methods in the control of soft hands, moving from the analysis of human behavior – as an unmatched standard of grasping dexterity [8], [9], [10]

These works represent an important step forward, not only in terms of performance, but more fundamentally for recognizing the complementary yet intertwined nature of machine learning methods and soft hands. Indeed, learning based techniques can only achieve solutions that are *close enough* to the desired ones, rather than exact. This uncertainty can be naturally compensated by the ability of soft hands to locally adapt to unknown environments.

The aim of this contribution, which is based on [11] and [9], is to build upon this principle, and fully exploit hardware adaptability to grasp a vast range of very different objects. To this end we propose a human inspired multi-modal, multi-layer architecture (Fig. 1) that combines feedforward components with reactive sensor-triggered actions. We extensively tested the proposed architecture on a set of 20 objects previously unseen by the network. The orientation of the objects placed

on a table also varied. We performed three repetitions for each condition, for a total of 111 tests, reaching an overall percentage of grasp success of 81.1%.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

Humans are able to accomplish very complex grasps by employing a vast range of different strategies [12]. This comes with the challenging problem of finding the right strategy to use for a given scenario. It is commonly suggested that the animal brain addresses this challenge by first constructing representations of the world, which are used to make a decision, and then by computing and executing an action plan [13]. Rather than learning a monolithic end-to-end map, we built the proposed architecture as combination of interpretable basic elements organized as in Fig. 1. The *intelligence* is here distributed on three levels of abstractions; i) high level: a classifier which plans the correct action among all the available ones, ii) medium level: a set of human-inspired low level strategies implementing both the approaching phase and the sensor-triggered reaction, iii) low level: a soft hand whose *embodied intelligence* mechanically manages local uncertainties. All the three levels are human-inspired.

We realized the classifier through a deep neural network. This was trained to predict the object-directed grasp action chosen among nine human-labeled strategies, using as input only a first-person RGB image of the scene. These actions were implemented on the robotic side (a KUKA LWR-IV arm endowed with a soft end effector, with a RGB camera placed on the top of the manipulator to simulate a first-person point-of-view, see Fig. 1) to reproduce the motions observed in the videos. A reactive component was then introduced, following the philosophy of [9]. This component take as input the accelerations coming from six IMUs placed on the soft hand to generate the desired evolution of the hand pose. The lower level of intelligence consists of the soft hand itself, which can take care of local uncertainties relying on its intrinsic compliance. Any robotic hand being soft and anthropomorphic both in its motions and in its kinematics can serve to the scope. Without loss of generality, we use here the Pisa/IIT SoftHand [14].

To conclude, the main contributions of this work are:

- A deep neural network, which is able to predict with high accuracy the strategy that a human would adopt to grasp an object, using a first-person RGB image of the scene. This result is then used to plan a suitable primitive execution on the robotic side;
- A set of reactive primitives that reproduce human grasps, substantially extending [9];
- The definition and extensive experimental validation of an autonomous grasping system, which combines these two blocks with the adaptability of a soft hand.

III. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

In this contribution, we present a data-driven human-inspired architecture for autonomous grasping with soft hands. We achieve this goal by: i) introducing a novel deep neural network that processes the visual scene and predicts which

action a human would perform to grasp the target object, ii) formulating and implementing an artificial counterpart of the strategies that we observed in humans, iii) combining them together in a integrated robotic platform, iv) extensively testing the proposed architecture in the execution of autonomous grasps. We finally discuss the importance of deep learning also for modelling human manipulation, to allow a successful translation for robotic control [15], and on the crucial part that an effective design and control of robotic wrist - *embodied machine intelligence* - can play for achieving meaningful grasps with soft end effectors [16].

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bicchi and V. Kumar, "Robotic grasping and contact: A review," in *ICRA*, vol. 348. Citeseer, 2000, p. 353.
- [2] L. Birglen, T. Laliberté, and C. M. Gosselin, *Underactuated robotic hands*. Springer, 2007, vol. 40.
- [3] C. Piazza, G. Grioli, M. Catalano, and A. Bicchi, "A century of robotic hands," *Annual Review of Control, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems*, vol. (In Press), 2019.
- [4] C. Erdogan, A. Schröder, and O. Brock, "Coordination of intrinsic and extrinsic degrees of freedom in soft robotic grasping," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [5] M. Haas, W. Friedl, G. Stillfried, and H. Höppner, "Human-robotic variable-stiffness grasps of small-fruit containers are successful even under severely impaired sensory feedback," *Frontiers in neurobotics*, vol. 12, p. 70, 2018.
- [6] X. Yan, J. Hsu, M. Khansari, Y. Bai, A. Pathak, A. Gupta, J. Davidson, and H. Lee, "Learning 6-dof grasping interaction via deep geometry-aware 3d representations," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–9.
- [7] P. Schmidt, N. Vahrenkamp, M. Wächter, and T. Asfour, "Grasping of unknown objects using deep convolutional neural networks based on depth images," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 6831–6838.
- [8] T. Nishimura, K. Mizushima, Y. Suzuki, T. Tsuji, and T. Watanabe, "Thin plate manipulation by an under-actuated robotic soft gripper utilizing the environment," in *Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), 2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on*. IEEE, 2017, pp. 1236–1243.
- [9] M. Bianchi, G. Averta, E. Battaglia, C. Rosales, A. Tondo, M. Poggiani, G. Santaera, S. Ciotti, M. G. Catalano, and A. Bicchi, "Tactile-based grasp primitives for soft hands: Applications to human-to-robot handover tasks and beyond," in *Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2018 IEEE International Conference on*. IEEE, 2019.
- [10] C. Choi, W. Schwarting, J. DelPreto, and D. Rus, "Learning object grasping for soft robot hands," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 2018.
- [11] C. D. Santina, V. Arapi, G. Averta, F. Damiani, G. Fiore, A. Settimi, M. G. Catalano, D. Bacciu, A. Bicchi, and M. Bianchi, "Learning from humans how to grasp: A data-driven architecture for autonomous grasping with anthropomorphic soft hands," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1533–1540, April 2019.
- [12] T. Feix, J. Romero, H.-B. Schmiedmayer, A. M. Dollar, and D. Kragic, "The grasp taxonomy of human grasp types," *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 66–77, 2016.
- [13] G. A. Miller, E. Galanter, and K. H. Pribram, *Plans and the structure of behavior*. Adams Bannister Cox, 1986.
- [14] C. Della Santina, C. Piazza, G. M. Gasparri, M. Bonilla, M. G. Catalano, G. Grioli, M. Garabini, and A. Bicchi, "The quest for natural machine motion: An open platform to fast-prototyping articulated soft robots," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 48–56, 2017.
- [15] V. Arapi, C. Della Santina, D. Bacciu, M. Bianchi, and A. Bicchi, "Deepdynamichand: A deep neural architecture for labeling hand manipulation strategies in video sources exploiting temporal information," *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, vol. 12, p. 86, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fnbot.2018.00086>
- [16] S. Casini, V. Tincani, G. Averta, M. Poggiani, C. Della Santina, E. Battaglia, M. G. Catalano, M. Bianchi, G. Grioli, and A. Bicchi, "Design of an under-actuated wrist based on adaptive synergies," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, May 2017, pp. 6679–6686.